

Supplementary File 1

Structured feedback form

During the development of the framework, the manuscript was sent to a group of volunteers at different career stages and from various countries and institutions outside the PIWG for a round of structured feedback. Besides the feedback and comments directly added within the text, the reviewers filled in a standardized questionnaire made in Microsoft Forms. The questions in this questionnaire are found in Table 1.

Table 1. Questionnaire for the structured feedback

Section	Questions	Question Format	Branch in questionnaire
1. General	Name	Free text	
	Email address	Free text	
	What is your background and level of expertise? (e.g., clinician, translational researcher and e.g. PhD candidate, postdoc)	Free text	
2. Overall	Is the framework written understandably?	Yes/No	if no, open text box for explanation
	Does the framework serve its purpose?	Yes/No	if no, open text box for explanation
3. Introduction, Scope, and Genetic therapies	Is the purpose of the framework clear?	Yes/No	
	Are expectations managed?	Yes/No	
	Is there enough background information provided or references given to be able to understand the framework manuscript?	Yes/No	if no, open next question
	What is missing or needs to be clarified?	Free text	
4. Condensed framework	Are all the main considerations discussed? If not, what is missing?	Free text	
	Is the division into the three sections clear and useful? Are the subsections clear and useful?	Free text	

	Is the division into a shorter overview in the main text and a longer, detailed supplemental text clear and helpful for the reader?	Free text	
5. Supplement 2: Examples	Do you agree with the standardized template?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Did the examples provide sufficient detail and information to understand how the framework can be applied?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Should any other examples be added? If so, which ones?	Free text	
6. Supplement 3: Detailed framework	Is the in-depth background sufficiently detailed overall?	Free text	
7. Supplement 3: Molecular considerations	Did you feel you had sufficient background knowledge to understand this section?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Was the level of technical detail appropriate for your expertise?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Were any molecular aspects missing from this section that should be added?	Yes/No	If yes, open text box for explanation
	Did you find the tools/resources (e.g., pLI, LOEUF, ClinGen scores) and their respective descriptions useful?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Are there additional resources, tools, or examples you think would strengthen this section?	Free text	
8. Supplement 3: Clinical considerations	Did you feel you had sufficient background knowledge to understand this section?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Was the level of detail appropriate for your expertise?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Are there any aspects missing from this section that should be added?	Free text	

9. Supplement 3: Practical considerations	Did you feel you had sufficient background knowledge to understand this section?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Was the level of detail appropriate for your expertise?	Yes/No	If no, open text box for explanation
	Are there more practical considerations that should be included?	Free text	
10. Supplement 4: Recommended resources	Are there resources you would add or remove from the recommended resources?	Free text	
11. Figures	Are the figures clear and understandable?	Free text	
	Did the figures support understanding and working with the framework?	Free text	
	Are additional figures needed or can figures be left out?	Free text	
12. References	Are we missing any relevant references and works from others that we should include?	Yes/No	If yes, open text box for explanation
13. Final questions	Do you think an additional round of structured feedback is necessary? (for changes to the structure or content of the framework, not for textual changes)	Yes/No	
	Is there anything else you would like to let us know?	Free text	